

One Stop Service In Order To Improve Community Service through Mall Public Service

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Abstract

The new public service through the Mall Public Service is the answer to the wishes of the public about fast, easy, safe, comfortable and integrated services. It takes high morale and fighting power to bring all Human Resources personnel to the level of change Mall Public Service is an integration of business processes, operational mechanisms, data sharing, management of Human Resources, infrastructure facilities that support the convenience of each visitor, especially for vulnerable groups, cooperation between the central government, regional governments, and the private sector A total of 24 agencies both central, regional, State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN), Regional-Owned Enterprises (BUMD) joined in this Public Service Mall. From here also, 168 types of services can be directly arranged, starting with police services, Social Security Administering Agency (BPJS) Health, labor, taxation, immigration, MSME galleries, banking, prosecutors, State electricity companies (PLN), Regional Water Companies (PDAM)), including licensing for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (UMKM). So, people do not need to go back and forth to many places to take care of many things. But, it is enough to come in one place, and the officers assigned at the Sidoarjo Mall Public Service are officers who are already trained, professional, and always friendly in serving. The goal is that the community is truly maximized when they receive services. As the existing program, namely prioritizing community satisfaction in service. So the officers stationed here are friendly people in serving the community. Where a good government is a government that serves, not ask to be served.

Keywords: one stop service, community, mall, public service, integration

Introduction

Minister of Administrative Reform and Bureaucracy Reform (PANRB) Syafruddin inaugurated the Mall Public Service (MPP) of Sidoarjo Regency, East Java, Tuesday, January 29, 2019. The existence of this Mall Public Service will answer the wishes of the public towards the licensing process that is fast, easy, safe, and comfortable .

A total of 24 agencies, both central, regional, State-Owned Enterprises (BUMN), regionally-owned Enterprises (BUMD), joined in this MPP. Types of services that can be directly administered, starting with police services, Social Security Organizing Agency (BPJS) Health, employment, taxation, immigration, banking, prosecutors, the State Electricity Company (PLN), Regional Water Companies (PDAM), including Micro Business licensing, Small and Medium Enterprises (UMKM). This Public Service Mall occupies a four-story building, equipped with a library, lactation room, internet network, children's playground, and facilities for people with disabilities. This 1,500-meter building is a multipurpose building in Sidoarjo Regency Government.

Sidoarjo regency government that continues to strive to change the bureaucracy for the better, one of them is by building Public Service Malls. Through this spirit, the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucracy Reform (PANRB) seeks to strengthen the legal basis for the construction of Public Service Malls to become a Presidential Regulation (Perpres).

The presence of the Mall Public Service is in line with the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE). This Mall Public Service adopts the new public service, building MPP is not easy. Because Mall Public Service Malls are not just moving services from each agency into one place, not just a magnificent building, not just convenient facilities. Mall Public Service is an integration of business processes, operational mechanisms, data sharing, human resource management, infrastructure facilities that support the convenience of every visitor, especially for vulnerable groups, cooperation between the central government, regional governments, and the private sector. The new public service through the Mall Public Service is the answer to the public's desire for licensing that is fast, easy, safe, and comfortable.

(<https://jatimnet.com/mpp-sidoarjo-diluncurkan-168-layanan-bisa-diurus-di-sini>)

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this case, public service refers to the term public closer to the understanding of society or the public. However, the public understanding inherent in public services is not entirely the same and congruent with the understanding of

society. Nurcholish (2005: 178) provides a public understanding as a number of people who have the right thoughts, feelings, hopes, attitudes and actions that are right and good based on the values of the norms they have.

Decree of the State Minister for Administrative Reform (Meneg PAN) Number 63 / KEP / M.PAN / 7/2003, provides an understanding of public services, namely all service activities carried out by public service providers as an effort to meet the needs of service recipients and the implementation of statutory provisions .

Furthermore, Oxford (2000) explained the notion of public service as *“a service such as transport or health care that a government or an official organization provides for people in general in a particular society.”*

Public Services, according to Albercht and Zemke (2005), mention the quality of public services is the result of interaction from various aspects, namely the service system, HR service providers and customers.

The function of public services is one of the fundamental functions that must be carried out by the government both at the central and regional levels. This function is also carried out by BUMN / BUMD in providing and providing services and or public goods.

In an effort to achieve the quality of service described above, it is necessary to develop public service standards, which serve as benchmarks for quality service. Setting public service standards is a phenomenon that applies both in developed and developing countries. In the United States, for example, it was marked by the issuance of executive order 12863 in the Clinton administration, which required all government agencies to set customer service standards (setting customer service standards). The contents of the executive order are as follows:

“Identify customer who are, or should be, served by the agency, survey the customers to determine the kind and quality of service they want and their level of satisfaction with existing service, post-service standards and measure result against the best bussiness, provide the customers with choice in both sources of services, and complaint system easily accessible, and provide means to adress customer complaints.”

The essence of the contents of the executive order mentioned above is an effort to identify customers who (must) be served by the agency, surveying customers to determine the type and quality of service they want and to determine the level of customer satisfaction with ongoing services, including postal service standards and measuring results with the best, providing various choices of service sources to customers and complaints systems that are easily accessible, as well as providing a means to accommodate and resolve complaints / complaints.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research design

This research will use a qualitative approach that is expected to provide a more complete and comprehensive perspective to produce an in-depth study of social phenomena / phenomena.

Research sites

The research location is in Sidoarjo City. The selection of research sites must have considered various aspects. Several locations of public open areas in the city of Sidoarjo will be selected as research locations.

Data collection technique

Data collection techniques carried out using: In-depth interviews (in-depth interviews). In-depth interviews will be conducted on a number of respondents in the community and officials who are directly related to services in mall public service, as well as documentation from several mass media.

Data Analysis Techniques

In descriptive research, the process of analyzing and interpreting data is not only done at the end of data collection or standing alone, but is also carried out simultaneously when data collection takes place in the field, so in qualitative research, it is often known as a cycle process. After obtaining information, an analysis is carried out to look for conclusions while then the next information is collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Sidoarjo Regency Public Service Mall is located at Jl Lingkar Timur, Sidoarjo, commencing operations on January 10, 2019. The services provided include Samsat, SIM, SKCK, Immigration, Regional Revenue Agency, BPN, BPJS Health, BPJS Employment, PDAM , Attorney General's Office, Ministry of Religion, East Java Bank, Telkom, PLN, and a number of other services. Mall Public Service opens at 08.00 WIB until 16.00 WIB

Sidoarjo Mall Public Service. This is in accordance with and in line with government programs in providing convenient services to the public. The multipurpose building or SSC used for public service malls is quite good and adequate, there is

supporting infrastructures such as parking facilities, cleanliness, and security, services are also optimal, to realize the integrity zone. And it is suggested that minimizing cash transactions, as well as understanding and compilation of SOP must be carried out in order to create ease and transparency.

The main purpose of opening a mall public service is indeed to provide convenience for the community in getting services. All services are centered at this place, so the community can easily get various documents or other arrangements needed in one place.

Sidoarjo Regency Mall Public Service is the realization of the signing of a joint agreement between the Sidoarjo Regency Government and the participants or a number of other agencies that open their services there.

In addition to public services, he said that Sidoarjo would also complement the Mall Public Service with shopping centers, culinary centers, and so on. All in one building (<https://surabaya.tribunnews.com/2019/01/10/mal-pelayanan-publik-sidoarjo-mulai-beroperasi>)

Sidoarjo Mall Public Service. Starting from the ID card services (KTP), licensing, and various other services that have been opened in each office, will be centralized in the Multipurpose Building. A number of local government agencies or organizations (OPD) are already there, such as the Population and Civil Registry Office, the Investment Office and the One-Stop Integrated Service and the Regional Tax Service Agency. In addition to the three offices, other agencies such as the Health Service, Library Services and other services related to services also exist. Likewise, dispendukcapil has opened a population administration services there. Where all community services will be placed at the Mall Public Service located in this Multipurpose Building so that the community is easier and no longer hassled in taking care of anything.

In that place, services from other agencies will also be opened. I am starting from the service owned by the Sidoarjo regency government, Sidoarjo Police Service, East Java Bank, to Immigration who can arrange passports for Sidoarjo residents.

"All become one at the Public Service Mall. All public services, from the Sidoarjo Regency Government and other agencies such as the Police, Immigration, and so on. At the Sidoarjo Public Service Mall placed officers who are trained, professional, and always friendly in serving. The goal is that the community is the right maximum when receiving services. As the existing program, which prioritizes community satisfaction in service, so that the officers placed here are friendly people in serving the community. (<https://surabaya.tribunnews.com/2019/01/02/seluruh-layanan-pemkab-sidoarjo-akan-pindah-ke-mal-pelayanan-publik-gedung-serbagunalingkar-timur>.)"

Services at the Mall Public Service attract public interest. Many residents choose to come to the Mall Public Service. As a result, the queue was full. The Population and Civil Registry Office counters (Dispendukcapil) are the most popular. In the near future, service counters will be added.

The result is that almost all services run smoothly. However, banking services have not been maximized because there are three national banks that have not yet opened services.

Regarding the queue before the Mall Public Service opens, some residents have already lined up. Especially population services. The reason is there are online queue restrictions. Residents who did not receive a queue were forced to come to the Mall. Public Service Mall attracts public interest. Many residents choose to come to the Mall Public Service. As a result, the queue was full. The Population and Civil Registry Office counters (Dispendukcapil) are the most popular. In the near future, service counters will be added.

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In addition, there were a lot of Dispendukcapil queues. Many residents are waiting to make the Mall Public Service full. While the online queue, Ari said that so far, the quota reached 100 people. The rest is given to residents who come to the Public Service Mall. Going forward, the quota for online queues will be added. "Plus 50 more while being evaluated every day," explained the Head of the One Stop Integrated Investment Service Office (DPMPSTP). Meanwhile, Secretary of Dispendukcapil said, his party had coordinated with the manager of the Mall Public Service. Dispendukcapil will get two additional counters. Well, the two counters are planned to be used to add the services of the District. At present, there are six districts that are served at the Mall Public Service. Namely Buduran, Sedati, Wonoayu, Tulangan, Tanggulangin and Jabon. "The two additions are for the Gedangan and Porong Districts," he explained.

The two sub-districts were deliberately chosen. Consideration based on distance. According to Reddy, residents of Gedangan and Porong are closer to the Mall Public Service than to the office, adding the counters is urgently needed. Its function is to reduce queues at the Dispendukcapil office. In the future, the Mall Public Service will serve nine districts.

Since opening on January 29, the increase in visitors has continued. The queue of visitors also appeared at several counters.

Such as Dispendukcapil counters and BPJS Health. Every day there are 100 to 200 people who come to take care of the needs. That number will increase.

(<https://radarsurabaya.jawapos.com/read/2019/06/09/140557/pelayanan-di-mpp-membludak-dispendukcapil-segera-tambah-loket>)

Inside the MPP building, the queue must not exceed the number of seats provided. Visitors must queue in front of the designated ticket window. Another solution can be done by optimizing online queues, the new system is already running. The aim is to facilitate citizens. Residents can choose the date and time before coming to the Mall Public Service. However, this system is not yet running optimally. The addition of the three sub-districts will increase the number of Public Service Mall queues. However, Dispendukcapil has prepared a solution by directing the community to wait outside the building, where there are seats that have been provided.
(<https://radarsurabaya.jawapos.com/read/2019/02/19/120279/antrean-online-di-mal-pelayanan-publik-belum-efektif>)

CONCLUSION

Mall Public Service is an integrated one stop service, which has the aim of making it easier for people who want to take care of documents and permits, Mall Public Service aims to improve services to the public more efficiently and easily.

The building which is the Sidoarjo Mall Public Service. Starting from the ID card/KTP services, licensing, and various other services that have been opened in each office office will be centralized in the Multipurpose Building.

A number of agencies or Regional Apparatus Organizations (OPD) have begun to provide services there. Officers stationed at the Sidoarjo Regency Mall Public Service are officers who are trained, professional, and always friendly in serving. Until now, since its inauguration in January 2019, the Mall Public Service was felt to be effective and very helpful in facilitating the community to obtain excellent and responsive services. Many conveniences were felt by the community, however, the Mall Public Service must continue to improve its services.

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